

Incidence of facial nerve injury after open reduction procedure in patients with mandibular condyle fractures: comparison between classical and modified transparotid techniques

Luciana^{1*}, Marjono Dwi Wibowo², Dwi Hari Susilo²

ABSTRACT

Background: The most frequent complication of open reduction surgery for condylar bone fractures is injury to the facial nerve branch which most often occurs in open reduction procedures using a transparotid approach using classic or modified techniques. The aim of the study is to determine the incidence of facial nerve injury after open reduction using the transparotid approach and modified transparotid approach in patients with mandibular condyle fractures at Dr. Soetomo Hospital, Surabaya, Indonesia.

Methods: This is a retrospective-observational cohort descriptive study conducted on 31 patients with mandibular condyle fractures obtained from visit data from the Surgical Emergency Department at Dr. Soetomo Hospital Surabaya during January 2021 to August 2023 using secondary data in the form of medical records.

Results: The research subjects consisted of 24 men (77.4%) and 7 women (22.6%) with an age distribution ranging from under the 3rd decade to the 6th decade with the highest number under the 3rd decade as much as 48.4%. Based on the location of the condyle fracture, in this study it was found that 16 samples (51.6%) were at the base condyle, 12 samples (38.7%) were at the neck condyle, and 3 samples (9.7%) were in the head condyle. Then as many as 25 samples (80.6%) of mandibular condyle fractures occurred on one side, and as many as 6 samples (19.4%) occurred on two sides. In this study, there was an insignificant difference between the two techniques studied regarding the duration of surgery ($p=0.540$) and length of treatment ($p=0.628$) as well as a significant difference between the two techniques studied, where in the modified technique, the tendency for nerve injury to occur was smaller when compared with classical techniques ($p<0.05$).

Conclusion: The incidence of facial nerve injury was found to be lower in the modified transparotid technique than in the transparotid technique. The modified transparotid technique can be considered for use in patients with mandibular condyle fractures, both at the base condylar, neck condylar, and at the head condylar, because it is considered safe, easy, and has a low risk of facial nerve injury compared to the transparotid technique.

Keywords: facial nerve injury, open reduction, mandibula, fracture.

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¹Specialist II Medical Education Program, Head and Neck Surgery Study Program, Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Airlangga, Surabaya, Indonesia;
²Head and Neck Division of Surgery Department, Dr. Soetomo Hospital, Surabaya, Indonesia.

*Corresponding author:

Luciana;
Specialist II Medical Education Program, Head and Neck Surgery Study Program, Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Airlangga, Surabaya, Indonesia;
dr.lucy_lucas@yahoo.co.id

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INTRODUCTION

Maxillofacial trauma is a trauma that is quite often found in all trauma incidents where mandibular bone fractures are the most frequently encountered fractures with an incidence rate of 41%, followed by the zygoma bone at 27.6%, the maxillary bone at 24.8%, and the nasal bone at 17.1%.^{1,2} Of all mandibular bone fractures, 29% - 52% are located in the condyle.³ Fractures in the mandibular condyle bone can cause disturbances in the temporomandibular joint function, causing symptoms of

malocclusion, disrupting the masticatory function and movement of the sufferer's mandible.⁴ Mandibular condyle fractures can be corrected with closed reduction and immobilization, as well as with surgery, namely open reduction and internal fixation. There are several surgical approaches in open reduction procedures, including intraoral, submandibular, retromandibular, preauricular, transparotid and rhytidectomy approaches.⁵

The most frequent complication of open reduction surgery for condyle

fractures is injury to the facial nerve branch due to manipulation of the fracture segment, the process of tissue dissection when it reaches the fracture site, and due to instrument pull. Facial nerve injuries are considered to reduce the patient's quality of life even though the fracture can be resolved, so many studies have studied the easiest to perform but relatively safe surgical approach to the possibility of facial nerve injury in open reduction of condyle fractures.^{5,6} One of the surgical approaches for condyle bone fractures is said to be easy but has a small risk of facial

nerve injury is the transparotid approach.⁷

Seeing the fairly high incidence of mandibular condyle fractures in Indonesia, as well as the importance of a surgical approach to achieve good reduction with minimal complications, at Dr. Soetomo Hospital is currently starting to develop a new approach for open reduction surgery in patients with mandibular condyle fractures, known as the modified transparotid approach. The principle of this approach is more or less the same as the classic transparotid approach, but with less involvement of the parotid gland and facial nerve so it is considered safer against the risk of facial nerve injury after the procedure. Therefore, researchers are interested in studying the incidence of facial nerve injury after open reduction between the transparotid approach and the modified transparotid approach for mandibular condyle fractures. The aim is to determine the incidence of facial nerve injury after open reduction using the transparotid approach and transparotid modification in mandibular condyle fracture patients at Dr. Soetomo Hospital, Surabaya, Indonesia.

METHOD

This research is a retrospective cohort study on patients with mandibular condyle fractures obtained from visit data from the Surgical Emergency Department at Dr. Soetomo Hospital Surabaya from January 2021 to August 2023. The sampling technique in this research was total sampling using secondary data in the form of medical records. The data was then analyzed using the SPSS 26.0 (Armonk Cropt, New York, USA) for Windows. The chi-square test was used to evaluate the difference between categorical variables. All values considered significant if $p < 0.05$.

RESULT

Characteristics of study participant

The research subjects consisted of 24 men (77.4%) and 7 women (22.6%) with an age distribution ranging from under the 3rd decade to the 6th decade with the highest number under the 3rd decade as much as 48.4%. In this study, it was found that 26 samples (83.9%) had maxillofacial fractures other than mandibular condyle

Table 1. Characteristics of study participant

Characteristics	Number	Percentage
Gender		
Male	24	77.4
Female	7	22.6
Age		
<30	15	48.4
30 - 39	6	19.4
40 - 49	1	3,2
50 - 59	8	25.8
≥ 60	1	3,2
Other maxillofacial fractures		
Yes	26	83.9
No	5	16.1
Fracture elsewhere		
Yes	6	19.4
Fracture location		
Base condyle	16	51.6
Head condyle	3	9.7
Neck condyle	12	38.7
Fracture side		
One side (unilateral)	25	80.6
Both sides (bilateral)	6	19.4

Table 2. Operation duration and length of treatment days for both techniques

Variable	Technique		p-value
	Classic	Modification	
Number of Patients	16 (51.6%)	15 (40.6%)	
Duration (minutes)			
Minimal	94	150	0.540
Maximum	498	400	
Mean	284.4	263.7	
Median	280	260	
Length of stay (days)			
Minimal	3	3	0.628
Maximum	16	8	
Mean	5,6	5.3	
Median	5	5	

Table 3. Postoperative HBFNGS scores for both techniques

Variable	n	Technique		P value
		Classic	Modification	
Number of patients	31	16	15	
Postoperative HBFNGS score				
Grade I	14	10	14	0.035*
Grade II	3	2	1	
Grade III	2	2	0	
Grade IV	2	2	0	
HBFGNS score 3 months postoperatively				
Grade I	26	12	14	0.203
Grade II	3	2	1	
Grade III	0	0	0	
Grade IV	2	2	0	

*Significant ($p < 0.05$)

fractures, and 5 samples (16.1%) did not have other maxillofacial fractures. Meanwhile, for fractures in places other than the maxillofacial, the majority of samples did not have fractures other than maxillofacial fractures (25 samples, 80.6%) and as many as 6 samples (19.4%) had fractures in places other than maxillofacial fractures. Based on the location of the condyle fracture, in this study it was found that 16 samples (51.6%) were in the base condyle, 12 samples (38.7%) were in the neck condyle, and 3 samples (9.7%) were in the head condyle. Then as many as 25 samples (80.6%) of mandibular condyle fractures occurred on one side, and as many as 6 samples (19.4%) occurred on two sides.

Comparison of operation duration and length of treatment days in transparotid and modified transparotid techniques

A total of 16 samples (51.6%) underwent open reduction using classical techniques and 15 samples (40.4%) underwent open reduction using modified techniques. In the classic technique, the quickest operation duration is 94 minutes and the longest is 498 minutes, with an average operation time of 284.4 minutes. Meanwhile, for the modified technique, the quickest duration of surgery is 150 minutes and the longest is 400 minutes, with an average duration of surgery is 263.7 minutes. Then in the classic technique, the shortest length of treatment days is 3 days and the longest is 16 days, with the average length of treatment days being 5.6 days. Meanwhile, in the modified technique, the shortest length of treatment days is 3 days and the longest is 8 days with an average length of treatment days is 5.3 days.

Comparison of postoperative House-Brackmann Facial Nerve Grading System (HBFNGS) scores in transparotid and modified transparotid techniques

From the results of this evaluation, 24 patients with grade I post-operative HBFNGS scores for both techniques were obtained (10 patients with the classic technique and 14 patients with the modified technique), 3 patients with grade II (2 patients with the classic technique and

1 patient with the modified technique), and 2 patients each in grade III and grade IV, all of whom used classical techniques. Meanwhile, the evaluation HBFNGS score after 3 months post-surgery for both techniques was obtained as many as 26 patients with grade I (12 patients with the classic technique and 14 patients with the modified technique), 3 patients with grade II (2 patients with the classic technique and 1 patient with the modification), there were no patients with grade III, and 2 patients with grade IV, namely the classic technique

DISCUSSION

The incidence of mandibular condyle fractures was found to be greater in the male group than in the female gender group, where in this study, 77.4% of the sample was male. This is in accordance with several studies in 2019 and 2020 which studied the distribution of maxillofacial fracture patients at Dr. Soetomo Hospital, Surabaya namely 80% of maxillofacial fracture patients are male.^{8,9}

In 2021, a study in Australia stated that the risk of traffic accidents due to motorized vehicles was greater for male drivers than for female drivers because in men, driving behavior is considered more aggressive than in women. This research also states that drivers under 20 years of age will have an increased risk of traffic accidents due to motorized vehicles due to lack of driving experience at a young age compared to older drivers.¹⁰ This is in accordance with this study where the majority of the sample is male and under 30 years old.

The mandibular condyle is a bone located in the maxillofacial system and is protected by several soft tissue components so that fractures in the mandibular condyle are caused by large forces or energy affecting the maxillofacial structure. Therefore, fractures of the mandibular condyle will often be accompanied by other maxillofacial fractures. This can be seen in this study, where it was found that 83.9% of the samples also had other maxillofacial fractures besides mandibular condyle fractures. However, researchers did not specifically study which maxillofacial structures accompanied the mandibular condyle fracture that occurred.

Meanwhile, for concomitant fractures other than the maxillofacial, in this study the majority of the sample, namely 80.6%, were not accompanied by fractures in places other than the maxillofacial. Another study stated that most maxillofacial fractures will be accompanied by fractures in places other than the maxillofacial.¹⁰ However, these studies studied all maxillofacial fractures and did not specifically study mandible condyle fractures as in this study. This difference could also be caused by the sample selection method in this study which was based on inclusion and exclusion criteria associated with facial nerve injuries.

The location of mandibular condyle fractures in this study was mostly the base condylar (51.6%), followed by the neck condylar (38.7%) and finally the head condylar (9.7%). This is in line with research by Dhupar in 2021 and by Kozakiewicz in 2023, which states that the majority of mandibular condyle fractures are located at the base condylar. However, in Kozakiewicz's study, the second most common location was the head condylar, whereas in this study the second most common location was the neck condylar, and the head condylar was only found in 3 samples. This is because there are differences in the etiology of mandibular condyle fractures between the study by Kozakiewicz and this study. In research by Kozakiewicz, the most common etiology of mandibular condyle fractures was violence (assault) which was associated with a trauma mechanism that occurred directly at the location of the condyle. Meanwhile, in this study, the overall etiology of mandibular condyle fractures was due to motor vehicle traffic accidents so that fractures that occurred in the mandibular condyle were due to indirect trauma or due to continued force originating from other maxillofacial bones. Research by Dhupar also states that the most common occurrence of mandibular condyle fractures occurs on one side. This is in line with this study, where the majority of condyle fractures occurred on one side (80.6%).^{11,12}

In this study, significant differences were found between the two techniques studied, where in the modified technique, the tendency for nerve injury to occur was

smaller compared to the classic technique (p-value 0.035). Of the 15 patients operated on using the modified technique, only 1 patient experienced a mild facial nerve injury (grade II). Meanwhile, with the classical technique, of the 16 patients operated on, there were 2 patients with mild facial nerve injuries (grade II), 2 patients with moderate facial nerve injuries (grade III), and 2 patients with quite severe facial nerve injuries (grade IV). All patients with mild facial nerve injuries (grade II), did not show significant improvement after evaluation 3 months postoperatively. This can be caused by the patient's non-compliance in undergoing post-operative rehabilitation because the patient feels that he is not experiencing any disturbance or reduction in the quality of daily life. Meanwhile, all patients with moderate facial nerve injuries (grade III) from the classical technique experienced significant improvement to normal (grade I) after undergoing rehabilitation for 3 months. Then for 2 patients with quite severe facial nerve injuries (grade IV) from the classical technique, it was found that there had been no improvement after evaluation 3 months after surgery and were still undergoing routine rehabilitation every week.

We found several other studies that used surgical techniques that were almost similar to the modified techniques in this study. The first study by Colangeli in Italy, who called his technique mini-retromandibular transparotid, stated that of the 15 patients who were treated, only 1 patient had a mild facial nerve injury and improved to normal after undergoing routine physiotherapy for 3 months after surgery.¹³ Then research by Arcuri in 2022 in Genoa, named their technique the modified preauricular transparotid approach, with a sample of 6 patients, and only found 1 patient who experienced a mild facial nerve injury in the mandibular branch and experienced improvement after 6 months undergoing physiotherapy.¹⁴ Researchers also found a case study by Bhat in 2022 in India, who studied a similar technique by naming the technique as a modified retromandibular approach. Of the 3 patients studied, none of the patients experienced complications from facial nerve injury.¹⁵

Supported by several studies with similar techniques, the researchers believe that the modified technique in this study can be a technique that can be widely used for patients with mandibular condyle fractures, both at the base condylar, neck condylar and head condylar. The modified technique does use smaller incisions than the classic technique but can reach the fracture location adequately, although in some cases, difficulties in performing ORIF will be encountered. The use of modified techniques can also be considered because the tendency for facial nerve injuries and other complications is less than the classic technique.

CONCLUSION

The incidence of facial nerve injury was found to be lower in the modified transparotid technique than in the transparotid technique so it can be considered for use in patients with mandibular condyle fractures, both at the base condylar, neck condylar, and at the head condylar, because it is considered safe, easy, and has low risk of facial nerve injury compared with the transparotid technique.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

All authors declare there is no conflict of interest regarding publication of this article.

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ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

This study has been approved by the Ethical Committee Dr. Soetomo Hospital Surabaya, Indonesia with ethical clearance reference number: 1428/LOE/301.4.2/VIII/2023.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION

All authors had contributed to manuscript writing and agreed for the final version of manuscript for publication.

REFERENCES

- Gurung G, Chapagain LP, Pokharel M, Thapa S, Parajuli SB. Pattern of Maxillofacial

- Injuries during Covid-19 Pandemic at Birat Medical College Teaching Hospital of Eastern Nepal. *Birat J Heal Sci.* 2020;5(2):1099–103. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3126/bjhs.v5i2.31413>
- Chaeruddin MB, Istikharoh U. Epidemiological overview of craniofacial trauma cases in ntb provincial hospital in september 2018 - september 2019. *Unram Med J.* 2020;9(1):37–42. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.29303/jku.v9i1.400>
- Hackenberg B, Lee C, Caterson EJ. Management of Subcondylar Mandible Fractures in the Adult Patient. *J Craniofac Surg.* 2014;25(1):166–71. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1097/scs.0000000000000498>
- Pickrell BB, Serebrakian AT, Maricevich RS. Mandible Fractures. *Semin Plast Surg.* 2017;31(2):100–7. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28496390>
- Tandon S, Verma V, Rashid M, Srivastava S, Singh AK, Sharma NK. Is the facial nerve at risk following surgical correction of mandibular condylar fracture: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Natl J Maxillofac Surg.* 2022/08/20. 2022;13(Suppl 1):S1–10. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36393942>
- Bhutia O, Kumar L, Jose A, Roychoudhury A, Trikha A. Evaluation of facial nerve following open reduction and internal fixation of subcondylar fracture through retromandibular transparotid approach. *Br J Oral Maxillofac Surg.* 2014;52(3):236–40. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.bjoms.2013.12.002>
- Ellis E, Dean J. Rigid fixation of mandibular condyle fractures. *Oral Surgery, Oral Med Oral Pathol.* 1993;76(1):6–15. Available from: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0030-4220\(93\)90285-c](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0030-4220(93)90285-c)
- Wiradana AGAAAA, Wiargitha K. Profile of maxillofacial injuries in Departement of Emergency Trauma and Acute Care Surgery in Sanglah General Hospital from January 2012 to November 2018. *Intisari Sains Medis.* 2019;10(2):227-299. Available from: DOI: [10.15562/ism.v10i2.401](https://doi.org/10.15562/ism.v10i2.401)
- Setiawan RB, Dwi Wibowo M. Profile of Patients with Maxillofacial Fracture in Emergency Department, Head-Neck Surgery Division, Dr. Soetomo Public Hospital Surabaya in 2020. *Ann Dent.* 2022;28:80–4. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.22452/adum.vol28no12>
- Cullen P, Möller H, Woodward M, Senserrick T, Boufous S, Rogers K, et al. Are there sex differences in crash and crash-related injury between men and women? A 13-year cohort study of young drivers in Australia. *SSM - Popul Heal.* 2021;14:100816. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34041353>
- Dhupar V. Fracture of the Mandibular Condyle [Internet]. *Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery for the Clinician.* Springer Nature Singapore; 2021. p. 1085–114. Available from: http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-1346-6_53
- Kozakiewicz M, Walczyk A. Current Frequency of Mandibular Condylar Process Fractures. *J Clin Med.* 2023;12(4):1394. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36835931>

13. Colangeli W, Carmelo C, Raffaella N, Daniela B, Ida B, Roberto C, Maria G. Mini-retromandibular transparotid approach to subcondylar fractures of the mandible A single Center clinical experience. *Annali Italiani Di Chirurgia*. 2019;90:244-251.
14. Arcuri F, Ferri A, Bianchi B, Laganà F. Modified Preauricular Transparotid Approach for Treating Mandibular Condylar Fractures [Internet]. Research Square Platform LLC; 2022. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-1909589/v1>
15. Bhat S V, Krishna VK, Periasamy S, Kumar SP, Krishnan M. Modified Retromandibular Approach for the Management of Condylar

Fractures of the Mandible. *Cureus*. 2022;14(8):e27697–e27697. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36081975>

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